

Nuculidae (Bivalvia) from King George Island (South Shetland Islands) with the description of a new species of *Ennucula*

Nuculidae (Bivalvia) de la Isla Rey Jorge (Islas Shetland del Sur) con la descripción de una nueva especie de *Ennucula*

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ABSTRACT

During the 31st Soviet Antarctic Expedition in 1986/87, two species of nuculids have been found in Ardley Cove, a bay on King George Island, one of which is new to science and is described herein: *Ennucula ardleyana* n. sp. This species was found at two stations alive as single individuals in the intertidal zone and in a water depth of 100 meters. *Nucula falklandica* Preston, 1912, the second species, is already known from this area. It was found at six stations with soft bottom and coarse sediment in water depths between 35 and 90 metres in Ardley Cove and Fildes Strait (between King George Island and Nelson Island).

RESUMEN

Durante la 31^ª Expedición Antártica Soviética en 1986/87, se encontraron dos especies de nucúlidos en Ardley Cove, una bahía de la isla Rey Jorge, una de las cuales se describe como nueva para la ciencia: *Ennucula ardleyana* n. sp. Esta especie se encontró viva en dos estaciones como individuos aislados en la zona intermareal y a una profundidad de 100 metros. *Nucula falklandica* Preston, 1912, la segunda especie, ya se conoce en esta zona. Se encontró en seis estaciones con fondo blando y sedimento grueso en profundidades de entre 35 y 90 metros en Ardley Cove y el estrecho de Fildes (entre la Isla Rey Jorge y la Isla Nelson).

KEY WORDS: Mollusca, Southern Ocean, Antarctica, King George Island.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Mollusca, Océano Austral, Antártida, Isla Rey Jorge.

INTRODUCTION

Species of Nuculidae Gray, 1824 (Bivalvia: Protobranchia) live in all oceans of the world from intertidal to

abyssal zones, mostly in silty mud (HUBER 2010). Presently, about 170 valid recent species in 11 genera are known

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(MOLLUSCABASE EDS. 2024). The genus *Nucula* Lamarck, 1799 contains 86 recent species (slightly more than 50 % of all species of this genus) accepted as valid (MOLLUSCABASE EDS. 2024). With 48 species, the genus *Ennucula* Iredale, 1931 also makes a significant contribution to the total number of species.

South of the Polar Front, only representatives of the genera *Nucula*, *Pronucula* and *Ennucula* are known in recent times (WHITTLE ET AL. 2012). The record of nuculid species in Antarctic waters is relatively rare (POWELL 1965; DELL 1972; LINSE ET AL. 2006). In particular, the scarcity or absence of nuculid species in otherwise quite extensive studies on the Antarctic molluscs indicates their relative rarity (NICOL 1966; EGOROVA 1982, 1984; ARNAUD ET AL. 1986; MÜHLENHARDT-SIEGEL 1989; HAIN 1990; ABSHER & FEJÓ 1998; NARCHI ET AL. 2002; ALDEA & TRONCOSO 2008; GORDILLO ET AL. 2017; OSORNO-ARANGO & CANTERA-KINTZ 2021).

In contrast to the two abyssal species *Nucula austrobenthalis* Dell, 1990 and *Pronucula notobenthalis* (Thiele, 1912), only *Nucula falklandica* Preston, 1912 is a relatively common species, especially in the Malvinas/Falkland Islands, South Shetland Islands, South Orkney Islands and Antarctic Peninsula (ENGL 2012). Other nuculid species do not reach the Antarctic and are restricted to the more distant peripheral regions such as the Strait of Magellan, the Malvinas/Falkland Islands, South Georgia or the Kerguelen Islands, such as *Nucula kerguelensis* Thiele, 1912, *Nucula pisum* G. B. Sowerby I, 1833, *Ennucula puelcha* (A. d'Orbigny, 1842), *Ennucula grayi* (A. d'Orbigny, 1846), *Ennucula eltanini* Dell, 1990 or *Ennucula georgiana* Dell, 1964 (see THIELE 1912; DELL 1964, 1990; LINSE 1999; VILLARROEL & STUARDO 1998; FORCELLI 2000; VALENTICH-SCOTT ET AL. 2020; ZELAYA 2005).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The nuculids reported in this study were collected by the second author in the eastern part of the Fildes Peninsula

on King George Island, South Shetland Islands, near the Russian Antarctic station 'Bellingshausen' during the 31st Soviet Antarctic expedition (1985 to 1987). All stations were located in Maxwell Bay. Water entering this bay originates from the Weddell Sea by east wind drift or from the Bellingshausen Sea by west wind drift, depending on seasonal water circulation and prevailing wind direction (GORDON & NOWLIN 1978). Water temperature and salinity were not measured but are likely similar to those found by TIAN ET AL. (2015). Water temperature in Ardley Cove was there in the range 0.72-1.36°C (mean: 1.02°C) and the salinity from 33.97 to 34.14.

The Fildes Strait, one of the sampling areas, is characterised by an extremely strong, tide-dependent current. The bottom of this area consists mainly of hard substrate, stones and rubble. The sediment of Ardley Cove, the second sampling area, consists of fine sand and silt, and in the intertidal zone (the tidal range is about 1 to 1.5 metres), third sampling area, there are boulder fields and littoral pools with rocky bottoms, some of which are covered with brown algae. All samples, except those from the intertidal zone, were collected using a dredge with an edge length of 0.3 m. The contents were sieved through a sieve with a mesh size of 0.5 mm. Samples from the intertidal zone were taken during low tide using a plastic tube corer (5 cm²). This method is extensively described by BICK & ARLT (2013). These samples were washed through a sieve with a mesh size of 0.2 mm. All samples were fixed in 4 % borax-buffered formalin.

The molluscs from these samples were hand-sorted under a low-magnification binocular (Zeiss Discovery.V8) and colour photographs were taken of selected samples at IOW using a microscope camera (AxioCam 105 color). High-resolution imaging was done on selected samples using the Scanning Electron Microscope at IOW (FESEM Zeiss Merlin VP compact with Gemini I electron column; acceleration voltage 5-15 KV; 5-axis stage with 3-70° tilt function; detectors: SE, VPSE, InLens SE,

BSD; Magnification: 12-2.000 000). The SEM samples were coated with Iridium or Gold, by using a Cressington sputter coater for high resolution imaging.

The holotype and paratypes of the newly described species are retained in

the Senckenberg Museum, Frankfurt am Main (SMF). The material of *Nucula falklandica* is kept in the reference collection at the Leibniz Institute for Baltic Sea Research (IOW), Warnemünde, Germany.

SYSTEMATICS

Class BIVALVIA Linnaeus, 1758

Family NUCULIDAE Gray, 1824

Genus *Nucula* Lamarck, 1799

Nucula falklandica Preston, 1912 (Figs. 1-10)

Nucula falklandica Preston, 1912: 637, pl. 21, Fig. 3; CARCELLES & WILLIAMSON 1951: 322; POWELL 1960: 169; Powell 1965: 367; DELL 1964: 139, Figs. 1-17; DELL 1990: 5, Figs. 8-9; RAUSCHERT 1991: 14; VILLARROEL & STUARDO 1998: 127, Figs. 1, 27-28, 68-69, 102-103; ENGL 2012: 37, pl. 1, fig. 2; ZELAYA 2015: 254

Not: LINSE 1997: 45 (as *Nucula* sp. with clear concentric-radial network structure); LINSE 1999 (based on LINSE 1997): 404; LINSE 2002: 115, pl. 17, Figs. 9.1.2 (1-5)

Material examined: South Shetland Islands, King George Island • 7 individuals; 62.2332°S, 58.9985°W; 70 m; 30 Jan. 1986; Fildes Strait, Stn. 7, dredge. • 6 individuals; 62.2000°S, 58.9472°W; 50 m; 9 Jan. 1987; Ardley Cove, Stn. 27, dredge. • 6 individuals; 62.2032°S, 58.9410°W; 35 m; 13 Jan. 1987; Ardley Cove, Stn. 30, dredge. • 4 individuals; 62.2032°S, 58.9395°W; 40 m; 7 Feb. 1987; Ardley Cove, Stn. 40, dredge. • 1 individual; 62.2032°S, 58.9397°W; 50 m; 1 Mar. 1987; Ardley Cove, Stn. 56, dredge. • 10 individuals; 62.2041°S, 58.9295°W; 90 m; 7 Mar. 1987; Ardley Cove, Stn. 58, dredge.

Remarks: Our material agrees well with the description by DELL (1990). The maximum shell length is 3.4 mm. The shell surface is sculptured with growth folds and radial ribs. The prodissoconch has a length of 360 μ m. The periostracum is yellowish-brownish and sometimes appears covered with ferruginous deposits. The hinge bears 7-8 anterior and 4-5 posterior teeth. The chondrophore is strong, trapezoidal and directed forwards.

DELL (1964) used material that exists in the British Museum (Natural History) under the incorrect designation *Nucula pisum* G.B. Sowerby I, 1833 from the Malvinas/Falkland Islands, noting that the type material cannot be found, the description by PRESTON (1912) is vague and inaccurate and the illustration of the outer shell view is not good. A syntype of the species is housed at Museum of Natural History in Paris (MNHN-IM-2000-38316). Thankfully,

photos were taken at our request, which allowed us to clearly confirm our identification of *N. falklandica*.

ENGL (2012) illustrated *Nucula minuscula* Pfeffer, 1886 *sensu* Melvill & Standen, 1907 (NMS 1921.143.686) sampled on the South Orkney Islands and kept in the National Museum Scotland, and identified it as *N. falklandica*. He also illustrated *N. falklandica* from the 26th Soviet Antarctic Expedition from King George Island, housed in the Zoological Museum Hamburg. RAUSCHERT (1991) published his findings from the 26th (1980-1982) and 30th (1984-1986) Soviet Antarctic Expedition from Ardley Cove near King George Island. The provenance of these records is almost exactly the same as that of the present study. At that time, he detected the species at 12 stations in water depths between 5 and 70 metres. In the present study we observed this species between 35 and 70 m.

The records by LINSE (1997, 1999 and 2002) for the Magellan region do not refer to *Nucula falklandica*. The description provided and the images given in LINSE (2002) clearly show a different *Nucula*

species, probably *Nucula pseudoexigua* Villarroel & Stuardo, 1998, although the distinction of that species from *Nucula carlotensis* Dall, 1897 is still unclear (see VALENTICH-SCOTT *ET AL.* 2020).

Genus *Ennucula* Iredale, 1931

Ennucula ardleyana n. sp. (Figs. 11-18)

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Type material. *Holotype*: South Shetland Islands, King George Island, 1 live-collected specimen (Figs. 11-12); 62.2025°S, 58.9187°W; 100 m; 28 Feb. 1986; Ardley Cove, Stn. 12, dredge; SMF 367275. *Paratypes*: • 1 live-collected specimen (Figs. 13-16); same data as holotype; SMF 367276. • 1 live-collected specimen (Figs. 17-18); 62.1969°S, 58.9357°W; Intertidal zone; 12 Feb. 1987; Ardley Cove, Stn. 47, core; SMF 367277.

Type locality: South Shetland Islands, King George Island, 62.2025°S, 58.9187°W; 100 m; 28 Feb. 1986; Ardley Cove, Stn. 12, dredge.

Etymology: The name refers to the type locality in Ardley Cove, King George Island, South Shetland Islands.

Diagnosis: Small species of ~1.8 mm, with posterior umbo. Umbonal angulation of ~120°. Ligament almost horizontal. Hinge with 4 anterior and 3 posterior teeth.

Description: Small elongated shell, length up to 1.8 mm; height up to 1.3 mm (holotype length 1.5 mm, height 1.1 mm), equivalve, subequilateral, rounded triangular outline, umbo posteriorly; surface whitish, transparent, with light yellowish glossy periostracum.

Prodissoconch: Flattened, with nearly circular outline, smooth; limit with dissoconch clear; length between 184 and 190 μ m and in height between 143 and 146 μ m (Figs. 17, 18).

Dissoconch: Globose, subtruncated in outline; pointed protruding umbo posterior of midline inclined posteriorly; convex dorsal- and ventral margins, prolonged anteriorly (Figs. 11,

12). Surface only sculptured by fine irregular commarginal growth stages and numerous fine growth lines. Lunula and escutcheon inconspicuous (Figs. 15, 16). Internally smooth and glossy with sharp margin (Figs. 13, 14); ventral margin smooth. Anterior and posterior adductor muscle scars not visible. Pallial line without sinus. Posterior and anterior parts of hinge plate with 3-4 strong teeth, rectangular in cross-section, projecting vertically from hinge; teeth near umbo very short. Resilifer elongated-trapezoid (Fig. 15).

Ecology: As only 3 individuals were found in 2 very different habitats, little can be said about the ecology of this species. One animal was found in intertidal shallow water between stones. Two animals were found in a water depth of 100 m with muddy sediment. The different sediments and depths could be an

(Right page) Figures 1-10. *Nucula falklandica* Preston, 1912, from King George Island, South Shetland Islands. 1, 2: left valve, Fildes Strait, Stn. 7, depth 70 m (length 2.1 mm); 3: posterior view of a complete shell, same locality (height 3.3 mm); 4: right valve, same locality (length 2.9 mm); 5: hinge of a right valve, same locality; 6, 7: specimen from Ardley Cove, Stn. 27, depth 50 m, views from right valve and dorsal side (length 3.1 mm); 8, 9: exterior of right valve and interior of left valve, same locality (length 2.6 mm); 10: hinge of another left valve, same locality.

Figuras 1-10. *Nucula falklandica* Preston, 1912, de la Isla del Rey Jorge, Islas Shetland del Sur. 1, 2: valva izquierda, estrecho de Fildes, Stn. 7, profundidad 70 m (longitud 2,1 mm); 3: vista posterior de una concha completa, misma localidad (altura 3,3 mm); 4: valva derecha, misma localidad (longitud 2,9 mm); 5: charnela de una valva derecha, misma localidad; 6, 7: ejemplar de Ardley Cove, Stn. 27, profundidad 50 m, vistas de la valva derecha y del lado dorsal (longitud 3,1 mm); 8, 9: exterior de la valva derecha e interior de la valva izquierda, misma localidad (longitud 2,6 mm); 10: charnela de otra valva izquierda, misma localidad.

Figures 11-18. *Ennucula ardleyana* n. sp., King George Island, South Shetland Islands. 11, 12: holotype, Ardley Cove, Stn. 12, depth 100 m (length 1.5 mm); 13-16: paratype (length 1.8 mm), same locality as holotype; 17, 18: paratype (length 1.7 mm), Ardley Cove, Lapidary Point, Stn. 47, intertidal zone.

Figuras 11-18. Ennucula ardleyana n. sp., de King George Island, Shetland del Sur. 11, 12: holotipo, Ardley Cove, Stn. 12, profundidad 100 m (longitud 1,5 mm); 13-16: paratipo (longitud 1,8 mm), misma localidad que el holotipo; 17, 18: paratipo (longitud 1,7 mm), Ardley Cove, Lapidary Point, Stn. 47, zona intermareal.

indication that this species is much more widespread, but could often be overlooked due to its small size.

Differential diagnosis: We present a comparison with the known species of *Ennucula* from Sub-Antarctic and adjacent territories of South America: the South Georgian *Ennucula georgiana* Dell, 1964 and species from the Strait of Magellan or Malvinas/Falkland Islands, such as *Ennucula puelcha* (A. d'Orbigny, 1842), *Ennucula grayi* (A. d'Orbigny, 1846) and *Ennucula eltanini* Dell, 1990.

Ennucula georgiana is larger (9–15 mm in length), heavier, dorsally and ventrally rounded, with posterior margin subangled about in the middle. It has 12 anterior and 7 posterior teeth. A specimen 2.7 mm long pictured at the Natural History Museum Rotterdam (RMNH.MOL.463998) already has 7 anterior and 4 posterior teeth. The resilifer is large, triangular and projecting anteroventrally. However, it is not certain that the identification is correct, since the location is Weddell Sea and not South Georgia. *Ennucula georgiana* is known so far from South Georgia (DELL 1964; ZELAYA 2005).

Ennucula grayi, known from central Chile, Patagonia (including Strait of Magellan) and the Malvinas/Falkland Islands (DELL 1964; LINSE 1997; VILLARROEL & STUARDO 1998; FORCELLI 2000; ZELAYA 2005; VALENTICH-SCOTT ET AL. 2020), is also distinctly larger (up to 20 mm), subovate, and is a very robust species. It has 20 anterior and 7 posterior teeth. The resilifer is large, conical and projecting anteroventrally. Even very small individuals (1.8 to 2 mm long) already have 5 or 6 anterior and 3 to 4 posterior teeth. The most striking difference between *E. grayi* and the *E. ardleyana* n. sp. described here is the shape of the resilifer (robust conical projecting from the hinge line into the mantle cavity, versus elongated trapezoid lying on the hinge line) and the outer shape of the shell, which already differs from *E. ardleyana* n. sp. in this juvenile size. At 211 to 224 μm , the prodissoconch is larger than that of the newly described species.

Ennucula puelcha occurs in Brazil, Uruguay, Argentina, Malvinas/Falkland Islands, and the Strait of Magellan (DELL 1964; VILLARROEL & STUARDO 1998; FORCELLI 2000; PASSOS & MAGALHÃES 2011; PASSOS ET AL. 2024). According to SIMONE (2009) and VALENTICH-SCOTT ET AL. (2020), this species is restricted to the Atlantic Ocean from Brazil to northern Argentina, with uncertain occurrence in southern Argentina and Chile. It is also larger (up to 13 mm); globular. It has 18 anterior and 8 posterior teeth. The main difference is its robust conical resilifer and its relatively blunt umbo (SIMONE 2009).

Ennucula eltanini is only known from the Strait of Magellan and western Tierra del Fuego from water depths between 307 and 544 m (DELL 1990; ZELAYA 2005). We examined material from the Strait of Magellan from depths between 253 and 462 m. It is a small species reaching 4.1 mm in length and 3.2 mm in height. The umbos are prominent and the resilifer is small, roundish and upright. It has 8–10 anterior and 5–7 posterior teeth. Juveniles of *E. eltanini* with lengths of 1.5 to 2 mm already had 6 to 8 anterior and 3 to 4 posterior teeth, which distinguishes it from *E. ardleyana* n. sp. With a diameter of 204 to 216 μm , the prodissoconch was larger than that of the newly described species.

All species mentioned above are the only known species of the genus *Ennucula* from the sub-Antarctic region near the Antarctic Peninsula (Scotia Sea, Patagonia (including Strait of Magellan) and Malvinas/Falkland Islands) and are more than 1000 km away from King George Island and separated by the Bellingshausen and Scotia Sea with water depth deeper 3000 m. *Ennucula ardleyana* n. sp. differs from all of them by its smaller size, the subtruncated shape and the much smaller number of anterior and posterior teeth and the elongated trapezoid resilifer lying on the hinge line. Considering the small size of this species, the relative robustness of the anterior hinge plate is striking.

DISCUSSION

Two species of the Nuculidae were found in waters near King George Island in this study: *Nucula falklandica* and *Ennucula ardleyana* n. sp.

The morphology of the studied specimens of *N. falklandica* is as reported by DELL (1990). Our material is 3.4 mm in maximum length and it has up to 8 anterior and 5 posterior teeth compared to 7-9 anterior and 5 posterior teeth reported by DELL (1990). The surface is sculptured with some growth lines and clearly visible stripes.

The present study has led to the discovery of a previously undescribed species and the first recent record of a species of the genus *Ennucula* of South Shetland Islands.

Of the 48 recent species of the genus *Ennucula* known worldwide, only very few are known with shell sizes smaller than 3 mm (HUBER 2010). The four smallest are *Ennucula interflucta* (Marincovich, 1973) from northern Chile with 1.5 mm, the Caribbean *Ennucula elongata* (Rhind & Allen, 1992) with 2 mm, the Atlantic *Ennucula granulosa* (A. E. Verrill, 1884) with 2.5 mm and the North American *Ennucula similis* (Rhind & Allen, 1992) with 3 mm. *Ennucula interflucta* lives in the intertidal zone, the others in water depths below 500 m. The greatest similarity can be recognised

with *E. elongata*, regarding the tooth formula and the resilifer structure. The shape of the shell, pointed posteriorly in *E. elongata* and rounded in *E. ardleyana* n. sp., is clearly different, although the size is the same. In addition, radial striations are visible in *E. elongata* (see RHIND & ALLEN 1992), but not in *E. ardleyana* n. sp. As mentioned in the introduction, no *Ennucula* species were found during the numerous Antarctic expeditions, although many of them also visited the study area in Fildes Strait and Ardley Cove (e.g. RAUSCHERT 1991; ENGL 2012). It is very likely that *E. ardleyana* n. sp. was overlooked in earlier studies due to its small size.

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BIBLIOGRAPHY

- ABSHER T.M. & FEIJÓ A.R. 1998. Morphology and ecology of bivalve molluscs from Admiralty Bay, King George Island, Antarctica. *Brazilian Archives of Biology and Technology*, 41 (4): 437-446.
- ALDEA C. & TRONCOSO J.S. 2008. Systematics and distribution of shelled molluscs (Gastropoda, Bivalvia and Scaphopoda) from the South Shetland Islands to the Bellingshausen Sea, West Antarctica. *Iberus*, 26 (2): 43-117.
- ARNAUD P.M., JAŻDŹEWSKI K., PRESLER P. & SICIŃSKI J. 1986. Preliminary survey of benthic invertebrates collected by Polish Antarctic Expeditions in Admiralty Bay. *Polish Polar Research*, 7 (1-2): 7-24.
- BICK A. & ARLT G. 2013. Description of intertidal macro- and meiobenthic assemblages in Maxwell Bay, King George Island, South Shetland Islands, Southern Ocean. *Polar Biology*, 36: 673-689.
- CARCELLES A.R. & WILLIAMSON S.I. 1951. Catálogo de los moluscos marinos de la Provincia Magallánica. *Revista del Instituto Nacional de Investigación de las Ciencias Naturales anexo al Museo Argentino de Ciencias Naturales "Bernardino Rivadavia"*: *Ciencias Zoológicas*, 2 (5): 225-283.
- DELL R. K. 1964. Antarctic and subantarctic Mollusca: Amphineura, Scaphopoda and Bivalvia. *Discovery Reports*, 33: 93-250, pls. 2-7.

- DELL R.K. 1972. Antarctic Benthos. *Advances in Marine Biology*, 10: 1-216.
- DELL R.K. 1990. Antarctic Mollusca with special reference to the fauna of the Ross Sea. *Bulletin of the Royal Society of New Zealand*, 27: 1-311.
- EGOROVA E. 1982. Biological results of the Soviet Antarctic expeditions, 7. Molluscs of the Davis Sea (Eastern Antarctica). *Explorations of the Fauna of the Seas [Исследования фауны морей]*, 26 (34): 1-142. [In Russian].
- EGOROVA E. 1984. Bivalve molluscs in Antarctica. *La Conchiglia*, 188/189: 18-23.
- ENGL W. 2012. *Shells of Antarctica*. Hackenheim: Conchbooks.
- FORCELLI D.O. 2000. *Moluscos Magallánicos Guía de Moluscos de Patagonia y Sur de Chile*. Vazquez Mazzini Editores, Buenos Aires.
- GORDILLO S., MALVÉ M.E. & MORAN G. 2017. Benthic mollusc assemblages in West Antarctica: taxa composition and ecological insights. *Marine and Freshwater Research*, 68 (11): 2095-2105.
- GORDON A.L. & NOWLIN W.D.J. 1978. The basin waters of the Bransfield Strait. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 8: 258-264.
- HAIN S. 1990. The benthic seashells (Gastropoda and Bivalvia) of the Wedell Sea, Antarctica. *Reports on Polar Research*, 70: 1-181.
- HUBER M. 2010. *Compendium of Bivalves 1*. Harxheim, ConchBooks.
- LINSE K. 1997. Die Verbreitung epibenthischer Mollusken im chilenischen Beagle-Kanal. *Berichte zur Polarforschung, Bremerhaven*, 228: 1-131.
- LINSE K. 1999. Mollusca of the Magellan region. A checklist of the species and their distribution. *Scientia Marina*, 63 (S1): 399-407.
- LINSE K. 2002. *The shelled Magellanic Mollusca: with special reference to biogeographic relations in the Southern Ocean*. Ruggell, Lichtenstein, A.R.G. Gantner Verlag KG, 252 pp. (Theses Zoologicae, 34).
- LINSE K., GRIFFITHS H.J., BARNES D.K.A. & CLARKE, A. 2006. Biodiversity and biogeography of Antarctic and sub-Antarctic mollusca. *Deep-Sea Research II*, 53: 985-1008.
- MOLLUSCABASE EDS. 2024. MolluscaBase. *Nuculidae* J. E. Gray, 1824. Available online from: World Register of Marine Species <https://www.marinespecies.org/aphia.php?p=taxdetails&id=204>, accessed July 22, 2024.
- MÜHLENHARDT-SIEGEL U. 1989. Antarktische Bivalvia der Reisen des FS "Polarstern" und des FFS "Walther Herwig" aus den Jahren 1984 bis 1986. *Mitteilungen aus dem Hamburgischen Zoologischen Museum und Institut*, 86: 153-178.
- NARCHI, W., DOMANESCHI, O. & PASSOS, F.D. 2002. Bivalves Antárticos e Subantárticos coletados durante as Expedições Científicas Brasileiras à Antártica I a IX (1982-1991). *Revista Brasileira de Zoologia*, 19 (3): 645-675.
- NICOL D. 1966. Descriptions, ecology, and geographic distribution of some Antarctic pelecypods. *Bulletins of American Paleontology*, 51 (231): 1-102.
- OSORNO-ARANGO A. & CANTERA-KINTZ J. 2021. Benthic molluscs collected in Western Antarctica during the "Caldas", "Admiral Padilla" and "Admiral Campos" expeditions, southern summers 2014-2015, 2016-2017 and 2018-2019. *Bulletin of Marine and Coastal Research*, 50 (Supl. Esp.): 187-212.
- PASSOS F.D. & MAGALHÃES F.T. 2011. A comparative study of the bivalvia (Mollusca) from the continental shelves of Antarctica and Brazil. *Biota Neotropica*, 11 (1): 143-155.
- PASSOS F.D., BATISTÃO A.R. & LIMA L.L.C. 2024. Checklist of marine Bivalvia (Mollusca) from Brazil, with descriptive analyses of their bathymetric and geographical distribution. *Zootaxa* 5488 (1): 1-94.
- POWELL A.W.B. 1960. Antarctic and Subantarctic Mollusca. *Records of the Auckland Institute and Museum*, 5 (3-4): 117-193.
- POWELL A.W.B. 1965. Mollusca of Antarctic and Subantarctic seas. In: van Miegheem, J., van Oye, P. (eds) *Biogeography and Ecology in Antarctica. Monographiae Biologicae*, Vol 15: 333-380, Springer, Dordrecht.
- PRESTON H.B. 1912. Characters of six new pelecypods and two new gastropods from the Falkland Islands. *Annals and Magazine of Natural History*, (Ser. 8) 9: 636-640, pl. 21.
- RAUSCHERT M. 1991. Ergebnisse der faunistischen Arbeiten im Benthal von King George Island (Südshetlandinseln, Antarktis). *Berichte zur Polarforschung*, 76: 1-75.
- RHIND P.M. & ALLEN J.A. 1992. Studies on the deep-sea Protobranchia (Bivalvia): the family Nuculidae. *Bulletin of the British Museum Natural History (Zoology)*, 58 (1): 61-93.
- SIMONE, L.R.L. 2009. Comparative morphology among representatives of main taxa of Scaphopoda and basal protobranch Bivalvia (Mollusca). *Papéis Avulsos de Zoologia*, 49 (32): 405-457.
- TIAN S., JIN H., GAO S., ZHUANG Y., ZHANG Y., WANG B. & CHEN J. 2015. Sources and distribution of particulate organic carbon in Great Wall Cove and Ardley Cove, King George Island, West Antarctica. *Advances in Polar Science*, 26 (1): 55-62.

- THIELE J. 1912. Die antarktischen Schnecken und Muscheln. In Drygalski, E. von (Ed.): *Deutsche Südpolar-Expedition, 1901–1903, im Auftrage des Reichsamtes des Innern*. Wissenschaftliche Ergebnisse Vol. 13. Zoologie 5 (2): 185-285, pls 11-19.
- VALENTICH-SCOTT P., COAN E.V. & ZELAYA D. 2020. *Bivalve seashells of western South America. Marine bivalve mollusks from Punta Aguja, Perú to Isla Chiloé, Chile*. vii + 593 pp. Santa Barbara: Santa Barbara Museum of Natural History.
- VILLARROEL M. & STUARDO J. 1998. Protobranchia (Mollusca: Bivalvia) chilenos recientes y algunos fósiles. *Malacologia*, 40: 113-229.
- WHITTLE, R.J., QUAGLIO, F., CRAME, J.A. & LINSE, K. 2012. Nuculidae (Bivalvia) in the Cape Melville Formation, King George Island, Antarctica, with an overview of the bivalve fauna. *Antarctic Science*, 24 (6): 625-633.
- ZELAYA D.G. 2005. The bivalves from the Scotia Arc islands: species richness and faunistic affinities. *Scientia Marina*, 69 (S2): 113-122.